

A guide to selecting high-performing antibodies for OGA (O60502) for use in western blot and immunoprecipitation

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Method

The standardized protocols used to carry out this KO cell line-based antibody characterization platform was established and approved by a collaborative group of academics, industry researchers and antibody manufacturers. The detailed materials and step-by-step protocols used to characterize antibodies in western blot, immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence are openly available on Protocols.io ([protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization](https://www.protocols.io/view/a-consensus-platform-for-antibody-characterization)) (1).

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC006084c008	CVCL_XQ53	HAP1	OGA KO

Table 2: Summary of the OGA antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µL)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab124807**	1092853-2	AB_10971848	recombinant mono	EPR7154(B)	rabbit	0.70	Wb, IP, Others
ABclonal	A24124**	6100008508	AB_3668909	recombinant mono	ARC65434	rabbit	0.00	Wb, Others
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP2-76848**	HO1018	AB_3698349	recombinant mono	JG40-05	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IP, Others
Bio-Techne (Novus Biologicals)	NBP3-26142**	O0312W	AB_3638331	recombinant mono	8D12	rabbit	0.50	Wb, Others
Cell Signaling Technology	60406**	1	AB_3665359	recombinant mono	E9C5U	rabbit	0.10	Wb
MilliporeSigma	ZRB2337**	Q4006796	AB_3698373	recombinant mono	1B3	rabbit	0.50	Wb, Others
Proteintech	14711-1-AP	00167963	AB_2143063	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.85	Wb, IP, IF, others
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-34807**	AC4649683B	AB_2848715	recombinant mono	JG40-05	rabbit	1.00	Wb, IP, Others
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-49925**	AC4649494	AB_3092868	recombinant mono	8D12	rabbit	0.50	Wb, others
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-52490**	AC4649691	AB_3248967	recombinant mono	23GB2270	rabbit	0.50	Wb, IF, others

Wb=western blot; IP=immunoprecipitation; IF= immunofluorescence, **= recombinant antibody, Others=other applications not tested here

Table 3: Table of secondary antibodies used

Company	Secondary antibody	Catalog number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Concentration (µg/µL)	Working concentration (µg/mL)
Proteintech	HRP-Goat Anti-Rabbit Antibody (H+L)	RGAR001	AB_3073505	recombinant polyclonal	1.0	0.05
Abcam	VeriBlot for IP Detection Reagent (HRP)	ab131366	AB_2892718	polyclonal	0.04	0.08

Figure 1: OGA antibody screening by western blot

Figure 2: OGA antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1: OGA antibody screening by western blot.

Lysates of HAP1 WT and OGA KO were prepared, and 30 µg of protein were processed for western blot with the indicated OGA antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are presented to show equal loading of WT and KO lysates and protein transfer efficiency from the acrylamide gels to the nitrocellulose membrane. Antibody dilutions were chosen according to the recommendations of the antibody supplier. Antibody dilutions used: ab124807** at 1/5000, A24124** at 1/5000, NBP2-76848** at 1/500, NBP3-26142** at 1/1000, 60406** at 1/1000, ZRB2337** at 1/1000, 14711-1-AP at 1/5000, MA5-34807** at 1/1000, MA5-49925** at 1/1000, MA5-52490** at 1/1000. Predicted band size: 102.9 kDa. **= recombinant antibody.

Figure 2: OGA antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed for 1 h using 0.5 mg of lysate and 2.0 µg of the indicated OGA antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for western blot with the OGA antibody ab124807** used at 1/3000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=6% starting material; UB=6% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. **= recombinant antibody.